

MODULAR INSTRUCTION INTERVENTIONS AND MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT OF GRADE 2 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of modular instruction intervention such as online and home visitation to the mathematics achievement of second grade students in Turbina Elementary School in Calamba Laguna, Philippines during the third quarter of the school year 2020-2021. This was in response to the learning gaps in modular distance learning amidst pandemic. The students were grouped into two experimental groups such as online and home visitation groups. The groupings were based on the learner enrollment and survey form administered by the researcher. Quasi-experimental research design using the pretest and posttest percentage score was employed to achieve the objectives of the study. The results of the pretest revealed that both groups, online and home visitation, were low performing students while the students who studied under modular instruction interventions performed high in the posttest. This finding implies that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of two experimental groups who studied under modular instruction interventions. Furthermore, the findings revealed that there is no significant difference between posttest performances of the students who undergo online instruction intervention and home visitation instruction intervention. Thus, it can be concluded that modular instruction interventions are an effective strategy in teaching mathematics and may improve the achievements of the second-grade students. Hence, it is recommended that the teacher utilize this as an alternative strategy in teaching students during modular distance learning.

Keywords: modular instruction, intervention, experimental group, pretest, posttest, Philippines